

Employee perceptions towards web-based human resource management systems in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Despite greater volume of theoretical foundations on technological influence on HRM, there has been little empirical evidence in the area of web-based electronic HRM systems. Further, all such empirical research attempts have been taken in the western world. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on web-based HRM systems in Sri Lanka is interesting, relevant and timely since there is an increasing interest in understanding technological influence on workers in non-western cultures, especially in an emerging economy that has a reputation for IT outsourcing. The purpose of the study was to investigate employee perceptions toward web-based electronic HRM systems in Sri Lanka. For the research, 30 firms with web-based HRM systems as a stand alone automation serving employees' HRM needs belong to service and manufacturing sectors operating in Sri Lanka were surveyed. The findings led to suggest that system usage is high and user satisfaction is moderate. The level of complexity of the system is moderate and it significantly correlates with system usage. When the age of the system in operation is less, it is more likely that the users were to be satisfied with it. Further, users did not perceive web-based electronic HRM system as a method of shifting administrative responsibilities of HRM activities to them.

Keyword(s): human resource management; information technology; system usage; user satisfaction; web-based HRM.

INTRODUCTION

The influence information technology (IT) has upon HRM is persuasive. The Web is changing every aspect of the way an enterprise conducts business, and HRM is one of the latest developments of Web enablement (Karakanian, 2000). Since the beginning of the 1990s organizations have introduced web-based applications for HRM purposes by transforming traditional HRM into a web-based/electronic HRM (web-based HRM or e-

HRM) (Hempel, 2004; Karakanian, 2000; Ruta, 2005). A web-based HRM system ties and integrates HRM activities to other corporate processes such as finance, supply chain and customer service. Its premise is that HRM is the owner of the strategy and, when required, it is the service broker as opposed to the provider. By the wise use of network technologies and various communication channels such as wireless, it inter-faces to the enterprise intranet and connects to HRM service suppliers and business partners (Karakanian, 2000). Hence, web-based HRM shifts the HRM department from its isolated HRM activities, and redistributes it to the organization and its trusted business partners. The main forces that drive organizations to seek IT-driven HRM solutions are identified as the need for cost reduction, higher quality services, and cultural change (Yeung and Brockbank, 1995). Therefore, the implementation of web-based HRM systems could be treated as a form of innovation.

However, literature has highlighted the slowness of the HRM function in utilizing IT in comparison with other organizational functions (Cerveny et al, 1993; Dunivan, 1991; Tansley and Watson, 2000; Kinnie and Arthurs, 1996; Hall and Torrington, 1996, Ball, 2001). Many scholars in the western world are calling for HRM practitioners to innovate in their IT usage (Fisher and Howell, 2004). When web-based HRM systems are relatively new with very little empirical research available concerning their operation or impact, the most of the extant literature on web-based HRM systems consists primarily of case studies and anecdotal information. Yet, theoretical foundations on technological influence on HRM suggest that the web-based HRM solutions have changed not only the administration of human resources but also changed organizations and work (Crandall and Wallace, 2002; Kovach et al, 2002; Lepak and Snell, 1998; Walker, 2001). However, there has been little empirical evidence on the effect of web-based HRM systems on the employee end-users. Though a few empirical research studies have been conducted on the use of web-based HRM in the western world (Dineen et al, 2004; Buckley et al, 2004), such empirical research

attempts have not taken off worldwide. Hence, more data is needed from countries other than the US and Western Europe, especially from Asia. The articles in the business press and practitioner-oriented journals in Sri Lanka suggest that many firms operating in the country are moving towards technology driven HRM environments. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on web-based HRM systems in Sri Lanka is interesting, relevant and timely since there is an increasing interest in understanding technological influence on workers in non-western cultures, especially in an emerging economy that has a reputation for IT outsourcing. From a practical standpoint results will provide practitioners with information that could enable them to make informed managerial decisions and design effective people management strategies in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the research setting is both progressive and international in nature as the paper explores a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in a global environment.

In the above context, the focus of this paper is on the discussion of the results of an empirical investigation into employee perceptions toward web-based HRM systems in Sri Lanka. The paper examines a number of specific questions. These include the type of web-based HRM modules (functionalities) deployed; the perceived usefulness of web-based HRM systems; user acceptance of web-based HRM systems in terms of user satisfaction and system usage; individual, organisational and system conditions that explain the level of user satisfaction and system usage; and the extent to which web-based HRM systems led to devolve HRM workload to employees. As an initial attempt, 30 firms with web-based HRM systems as a stand alone automation serving employees' HRM needs belong to service and manufacturing sectors operating in Sri Lanka were surveyed. The rest of the paper is organized in four sections. In the first section, relevant literature is reviewed and the framework of the study is presented. The second section describes the methodology adapted

for the study. The results are presented and discussed in the third section. The summary of the key findings, implications and research areas for further inquiry and understanding are presented in the concluding section.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND RESEARCH MODEL

Tannenbaum (1990) defines human resource information system as a technology-based system used to acquire, store, manipulate, analyze, retrieve, and distribute pertinent information regarding an organization's human resources. The main forces that drive IT-driven HRM solutions are identified as analogous to operational, relational, and transformational impact of IT on HRM (Shrivastava and Shaw, 2004; Snell et al, 2002). The operational impact of IT refers to the impact to organizations by way of alleviating administrative burden of HRM, lowering variable transaction costs and reducing head count within HRM function. The relational impact of IT refers to the impact that technology has on relationships that HRM function enjoys with its clients by influencing response times, service levels, and by providing decision support systems. Transformational impact of IT redefines the scope of HRM function by increasing the time that HRM professionals could have to engage in strategic HRM activities. Hence, the expectations of web-based HRM are originated from ideas about the endless possibilities of IT to facilitate HRM practices and about the endless capacity of HRM function to adopt IT. However, extant literature suggests that nearly half of all new technologies implemented in organizations fail (Aiman-Smith and Green, 2002). From an HRM perspective, failed implementation can be particularly disruptive as failures lead to skepticism about future change efforts (Fisher and Howell, 2004). Therefore, it is important to investigate how employee users perceive web-based HRM systems. For the purpose of this study a web-based HRM system is defined as a stand alone automation serving employees' HRM needs.

User satisfaction and system usage

There are many constraints in using a financial approach in assessing the success of a web-based HRM system in an organization. Therefore, some literature suggests assessing the success of an IT implementation through system usage (Davis et al., 1989; Igarria et al, 1997; Straub et al 1995; Thompson et al., 1991; Venkatesh and Ramesh, 2006) and user satisfaction (Amoroso and Cheney, 1991; Igarria, 1990; Ruta, 2005; Haines and Petit, 1997; Wu and Wang, 2006). The system usage is a measure of success to the extent that the system is used extensively provided it is perceived to be of value to the end-user and also perceived to be easy to use (Klenke, 1992; Fisher and Howell, 2004). Hence, the system usage reveals user acceptance of the web-based HRM system. With regards to the user satisfaction, as web-based solutions replace personal face-to-face interactions with computer-based information, some employees may view such systems with suspicion. Therefore, it is important to investigate how the system is perceived. The user satisfaction is based on attitudes and beliefs whereas the system usage is based on behaviors (Haines and Petit, 1997). Together, user satisfaction and system usage provide a more complete picture of the user acceptance of the web-based HRM system than if either measure was applied in isolation. Therefore, in this study, the acceptance of the web-based HRM system is measured by the system usage and user satisfaction. Some literature suggests that the system usage should be assessed in terms of web-site usage, for instance, by taking the number of hits on the entire site via system logs, documents viewed, visits, and single visitors in order to have a better representation of users and their use (Ruta, 2005; Venkatesh and Ramesh, 2006). However, the design of this study does not allow collecting accurate information about the web-site usage as this study relies on the employee end-users to provide data. Therefore, the system usage is measured based on one's overall feeling about the degree of usage of the system over a normal period of one month duration. With regard to user satisfaction, it is defined as the sum of one's feelings and

attitudes toward a variety of factors related to the delivery of information products and services (Wu and Wang, 2006). Therefore, the user satisfaction is measured based on one's overall feeling about the degree of satisfaction with the system (refer Appendix I). The conceptual framework developed for the research is shown in Figure 1.

INSERT FIGURE 1 ABOUT HERE

A number of conditions could help to explain the level of user satisfaction and system usage and ultimately the acceptance of the web-based HRM system. Borrowing from Haines and Petit's (1997) terminology those conditions were classified into organizational characteristics, system conditions and performance, and individual characteristics. Some of the variables identified by Haines and Petit (1997) in connection to human resource information systems along with several additional variables, which are expected to be related to web-based HRM systems, are taken into account in developing the framework for the research.

Organizational characteristics

Literature review led to identify organizational characteristics that influence the user satisfaction and system usage. The factors such as organizational culture, the nature of the ownership of the firm, technology strategy, the nature of the technology and IT infrastructure, the availability of internal support for employees, the size of the organization, and industrial sector of the organization could influence the user satisfaction and system usage (Haines and Petit, 1997; Ruta, 2005; Shrivastava and Shaw, 2004). However, as an initial attempt it was decided to confine the study to investigate three organizational characteristics, namely, workforce size, industrial sector and the age of the web-based HRM system. Literature identify an organization's workforce size (referred to as the size of the organization) as a clear determinant of whether it has an IT driven system at all and the number of HRM

modules it has (Ball, 2001; Haines and Petit, 1997; Laukkanen et al., 2007; Shrivastava and Shaw, 2004). The organization's industry or the sector can also be considered as another characteristic (Armenakis and Bedeian, 1999). Other than these two characteristics, this study further assumes that the amount of time the web-based HRM has been in place (referred to as the age of the web-based HRM system) could also influence the user satisfaction and system usage.

System conditions and performance

The decisions relating to system conditions and performance are often being made based on cost and other technical considerations without conscious thought on how these conditions will be perceived by the users (Fisher and Howell, 2004). Hence, several system characteristics could influence the user satisfaction and system usage. For instance, vendor is a system condition, where vendors could be ranked on the functionality of their software, the degree to which the software satisfies employee needs, the technical infrastructure required to operate and deploy the software, etc. (Ball, 2001; Fisher and Howell, 2004; Shrivastava and Shaw, 2004; Grant et al., 2006). The level of complexity is another system characteristic. The benefits of complex designs generally include enhanced features, increased data integrity, and complete administrative reporting. However, Aiman-Smith and Green (2002) found that more complex technologies were associated with lower user satisfaction. Further, literature identifies perceived usefulness, i.e., users' level of conviction (or belief) that a particular system will increase users' work performance, as a system performance characteristic (Davis et al, 1989, Ruta, 2005). It is suggested that users who perceive that the system to be useful would use the system to a great extent (Haines and Petit, 1997). In this research, system conditions and performance refers to product type (custom-made or an off-the-shelf solution), the level of system complexity, and the perceived usefulness of the system.

Individual characteristics

In a web-based HRM environment, individual users have to establish a new kind of relationship with the HRM function, as well as have to accept interaction with a computer rather than with a person, and, for some, using a new technology. The extant literature suggests that individual characteristics such as age, gender, and prior exposure to IT based HRM system could influence the user satisfaction and system usage (Bajaj and Nidumolu, 1998; Haines and Petit, 1997; Fuerst and Cheney, 1982; Igbaria and Nachman, 1990; Venkatesh and Morris, 2000).

The purpose of web-based HRM system and devolvement of HRM workload to employees

The purpose of the system includes both the stated purpose and implied purpose (Fisher and Howell, 2004). Organizations should be clear on the purpose of the web-based HRM system and any resulting effects such as the system creating perceived additional work or burden for an employee. For instance, self-service modules are often used to shift responsibility for administrative HRM activities from an HRM administrator to the employees, which could be perceived either as an easier and less time-consuming process for completing forms and updating information (Jossi, 2001) or another cost-saving mechanism, requiring employees to perform tasks that should be performed by an administrator (Brown, 2003). However, by relieving HRM personnel from clerical transaction duties open avenues for them to perform strategic functions and to become a strategic partner (Kovach et al, 2002). What ever the purpose, the web-based HRM work environment demands a high degree of employee and line manager involvement (Starcke, 1997). Therefore, it is important to identify employee perceptions on the extent to which web-based HRM systems led to devolve HRM workload to employees.

METHODOLOGY

Sample

The sample for the study was selected from the firms that use web-based HRM system as a stand alone automation serving employees' HRM needs. Though this restriction excluded the firms where web-based HRM is a component in a larger ERP presence, it led to specify the nature of the system that is referred to as web-based HRM in this study. Further, when defining the "user" for the study purposes, the review of literature led to identify two types of users, i.e., users who directly involve in people management activities (i.e., HRM users who are from the HRM department/unit) and who do not (i.e., Non-HRM users). The literature identify that there are differences in the technology acceptance and adoption by Non-HRM employee end-users and tool level users attached to HRM departments. Because these two groups are not equivalent, their perceptions about the same software package might be completely different. Therefore, as an initial attempt it was decided to confine the sample to end-users who interact with the web-based HRM system to do their work but not involved in people management activities of the organization (Non-HRM end-users).

The sample selection was in two stages. As the first stage, a sample of private sector firms was identified from a telephone directory through initial contacts made over the telephone that fulfilled the selection criteria, i.e., 1) a firm should have a web-based HRM system as a stand alone automation serving employees' HRM needs and it should be functioning for at least one year; 2) should have implemented at least four web-based HRM modules; 3) should have end-users who interact with the web-based HRM system to do their work but not involved in people management activities of the organization (Non-HRM end-users); 4) for the users (Non-HRM end-users), the use is not mandated and the web-based HRM system is not the sole access point to the HRM functionality. This restriction is imposed as the factors that influence usage would be irrelevant if the use is mandated or the

web-based HRM system is the sole access point to the HRM functionality. Hence, sample was confined to firms that provide users with alternatives to do their work and users can choose freely whether to use the web-based HRM system or not to get their work done. Being an Asian developing country, only about 45 firms operating in the country that belong to service and manufacturing sectors fulfilled the criteria. All of those firms are located in Colombo, which is considered as the main business hub of the country. Of those 45 firms, a random sample of 30 firms was selected. As the second stage, from those randomly selected firms, a random sample of employees was selected who fulfilled the criteria set for the study. In selecting the sample, initial contacts were made with three employee users who were not working in the same managerial function using simple random sample method. Of the 150 self-administered questionnaires distributed, 72 respondents voluntarily responded within 4 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution, which started in March 2007. A total of 68 usable responses resulted in 45 per cent response rate.

With regard to organizational characteristics, 47 per cent employed between one to 500 employees and 53 per cent employed over 500 employees. With regard to the age of the web-based HRM system, 24 per cent of the firms implemented their web-based HRM systems less than five years ago while 76 per cent implemented more than five years ago. 64 per cent came from diversified services sector while 36 per cent from manufacturing sector. With regard to system conditions, 60 per cent had off-the-shelf solutions while 40 per cent had custom-made solutions as the product type. For 26 per cent of the respondents, their web-based HRM system was very high in complexity, for 20 per cent it was high, for 47 per cent it was moderate, and for seven per cent it was low in complexity. With regard to respondents' characteristics, 62 per cent were women. 78 per cent belong to the age group of 35 years or below. 39 per cent had prior exposure to IT-based HRM systems at their previous workplaces.

Measurement of variables, instrument and the methods of data analysis

The self-administered questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection. The survey questionnaire was designed covering the aspects related to the web-based HRM system that are outlined in the earlier sections. The most of the responses were recorded on Likert type five point response scale. Demographic data was collected as categorical variables. Gender coded as Female=0, Male= 1, Age coded as 35 years or bellow=0; Above 35 years=1; Prior experience with IT-based HRM systems at previous workplaces coded as No=0, Yes=1; Size of the organization coded as 1-500=0, More than 500=1; Sector of the organization coded as Service=0, Manufacturing=1; Age of the web-based HRM system coded as 5 years or less=0, More than 5 years=1; and Product type coded as Off-the-shelf=0, Customized=1. The measures used for the measurement of variables are given in Appendix 1. Considering the literacy of the target population and the amenability of the research questions, the questionnaire was constructed in English language. The questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample of 10 employees that fit with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. The pre-tested survey questionnaire after amendments was administered among the respondents. Participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. The analysis of the survey data was conducted using SPSS. In addition to descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, correlation and stepwise multiple regression analysis was used. Factor analysis was not performed to identify the underlying dimensions of the variables as the number of respondents is low. To determine how independent variables predict the two dependant variables, stepwise multiple regression was performed. Since each variable is entered into the equation in turn in the stepwise regression procedure, the individual contribution of each variable to R-square is calculated and the statistical significance of that contribution is

assessed. In interpreting results, R-square (adjusted) statistic and standardized coefficients were used.

RESULTS

The study investigated the availability and the usage of 18 web-based HRM modules. It was found that personal data maintenance ($\bar{X} = 4.88$), reports and statistics ($\bar{X} = 4.05$), payroll and benefits ($\bar{X} = 4.69$) and attendance maintenance ($\bar{X} = 4.34$) have a high level of usage and these modules are in operation in more than 85 per cent of the firms. Though modules of e-learning ($\bar{X} = 4.23$), document management ($\bar{X} = 4.66$) and performance management ($\bar{X} = 3.94$) have a high level of usage, these modules are in operation in around 40 per cent of the firms. Further, though modules of information sharing ($\bar{X} = 3.98$) and job evaluation ($\bar{X} = 2.62$) were in operation in about 60 per cent of firms these modules do not reveal a high level of usage.

With regard to the extent to which web-based HRM system led to devolve HRM workload to employees, the items “dependency on HR department” ($\bar{X} = 2.72$), “increased HRM related workload of line managers” ($\bar{X} = 2.13$) and “increased workload of employees” ($\bar{X} = 2.48$) scored low mean values. These results led to suggest that employees perceive less dependence on the HRM department and they perceive low levels of increased amount of workload due to web-based HRM systems.

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for study variables. The mean values suggest that the perceived usefulness is high for all most all variables, the level of complexity is moderate, the user satisfaction is moderate, and system usage is high.

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Mean comparisons were used to determine whether there are significant differences in the user satisfaction and system usage by organizational and individual characteristics. The results of the t-test led to suggest that there are no significant differences in the system usage by either organizational characteristics or individual characteristics. However, the results showed differences in the user satisfaction by two organizational characteristics, i.e., the sector of the firm ($t=2.99$, $p<0.01$) and the age of the web-based HRM system ($t=5.42$, $p<0.001$). The respondents from the manufacturing sector showed a higher level of satisfaction than the respondents from the service sector; when the age of the system is less than 5 years, the respondents showed a higher level of satisfaction than when the age of the system is more than 5 years.

The correlations among study variables are also shown in Table 1. As that can be seen in Table 1, the age of the web-based HRM system is an important characteristic for the user satisfaction. The product type is not significantly correlated with either system usage or user satisfaction. The level of complexity of the system correlates significantly with the system usage. With regard to the perceived usefulness of web-based HRM systems, all time related variables explained the system usage significantly. Although a weak relationship is found between cost savings and the user satisfaction, the link with the system usage is much strong. Organizational performance related variables such as faster reactions to problems/opportunities and the increased amount of available data are important conditions for the increased user satisfaction while all most all organizational performance related variables are important conditions for the increased system usage. Overall, correlation analysis suggests that users would use the system more when the system as a whole is perceived to be less complicated than otherwise. Further, all the perceived usefulness related variables led to increase the system usage.

To determine how independent variables predict the user satisfaction and system usage, multiple regression was performed with stepwise selection of variables. It was found that “increased amount of available data” explains 73 percent ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.726$, $\beta=0.864$, $p<0.01$) of the variance in user satisfaction. With regard to the system usage, it was found that “enabled rapid communications” along explained 73 percent ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.734$, $\beta=0.869$, $p<0.01$) of the variance in the system usage. Further, “enabled rapid communications” ($\beta=0.731$, $p<0.01$) together with “better access to needed data” ($\beta=0.488$, $p<0.05$) explained 97 percent ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.969$, $\Delta R^2 = 0.237$, $p<0.001$) of the variance in the system usage.

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The paper presented the results of a research on web-based HRM systems in Sri Lanka. As the number of empirical research studies that investigated web-based HRM systems is limited and as this research investigated how employees of web-based HRM systems in an emerging developing country in Asia perceive their systems, the results of this research are of interest to both academics and practitioners for several reasons.

The web-based HRM system acceptance is assessed based on the user satisfaction and system usage. The findings led to reveal that the system usage is high. This supports the view that web-based HRM systems are perceived to be of value to the end user (see- Klenke, 1992; Fisher and Howell, 2004). Further, the findings revealed that the level of complexity is moderate. The moderate level of system complexity reveals perception towards the ease of use. Furthermore, the level of complexity correlates significantly with the system usage. However, in this study all the variables including the level of complexity were measured globally rather than elementally. In future research, the measure of complexity could be taken for each module and could investigate the effect of each module on work amount. Further, one could argue that the complexity is a function of both the system and the individuals using

it. In this regard, the sample selection is such that for the users the use is not mandated and the web-based HRM system is not the sole access point to the HRM functionality. In this context, the high level of system usage could be explained based a notion in literature. That is, due to social influence, to be part of the organization, respondents are inclined to accept the web-based HRM system through subjective norms when they see their colleagues doing so (see- Fulk, 1993; Ajzen, 1991; Taylor and Todd, 1995). The findings of the study also highlight the time related, cost related and organizational performance related conditions that support the system usage and user satisfaction. For instance, the findings led to suggests that faster reactions to problems/opportunities and the increased amount of available data are important conditions for the increased user satisfaction and system usage. However, one could argue that the user satisfaction and system usage are important conditions for increasing organizational performance related variables, which could not be justified based on correlations. Hence, the user satisfaction and system usage deserves more thought in future research. Though several past studies found the importance of individual and organizational characteristics in explaining the system usage, those had not predicted the system usage in this study. Further, the factors such as organizational culture and the availability of internal support for users were not enquired. If such factors could also be included in future research, the levels of user satisfaction and system usage that stem from those could also be taken into account.

The findings revealed that the user satisfaction is moderate. The level of complexity does not correlate significantly with the user satisfaction. Further, employees did not perceive the web-based HRM system as a method of shifting responsibility for administrative HRM activities to them. Furthermore, the results revealed that when the age of the web-based HRM system in operation is less, it is more likely that the users were to be satisfied with it. This suggests either more recent systems are better designed and better suited to the needs of the

users, or satisfaction goes down with the age of the system because users become accustomed to it and forget about the benefits over the manual system. The findings of the study highlighted the conditions that support user satisfaction. The user satisfaction is explained by only one organizational performance related variable. Though several past studies such as Haines and Petit (1997) found the importance of individual characteristics in explaining user satisfaction, any of the individual characteristics had not explained user satisfaction in the Sri Lankan context. Further, the extant literature identifying the organizational workforce size as an important predictor in IT-enabled HRM is mixed (see- Ball, 2001; Haines and Petit, 1997).

Though past research has not been clearly demonstrated the strength of the relationship between the user satisfaction and system usage, in the study, it is expected that high user satisfaction would lead to high system usage. However, a weak correlation was found between the two dependent variables. This suggests that a high level of user satisfaction does not translate into a high level of system usage. In this regard, on one hand, system usage could have been measured independently of the user by taking the number of hits on the entire site via system logs or could have attempted to distinguish the rare but thorough user from the frequent but discretionary user. On the other hand, the respondents of the study were end-users who interact with web-based HRM systems to do their work but not involved in people management activities of the organization (Non-HRM end-users). Therefore, it would not be a surprise to find that a higher level of satisfaction does not create a higher level of usage as the respondents of the study are not HRM professionals (tool level users). In this regard, literature suggests that there could be differences in technology adoption between end-users and tool level users and also their perceptions about the same software package might be completely different. Therefore, this opens an area for future research of comparative nature investigating whether there are similarities/differences in the web-based HRM adoption by Non-HRM and HRM users.

Further, employees did not perceive the web-based HRM system as a method of shifting responsibility for administrative HRM activities to them. Further, employee perception was that the web-based HRM system results in a low level of additional HRM related workload to line managers. Furthermore, they perceive that the web-based HRM system led to lower the level of dependency on the HRM department. Technology and HRM have broad influences upon each other. In this regard, Snell et al. (2002) suggested that the HRM function can meet the challenge of simultaneously becoming more strategic, flexible, cost-efficient, and customer-oriented by leveraging on IT. Therefore, HRM professionals must be able to adopt technologies that allow the reengineering of the HRM function, be prepared to support organizational and work-design changes enabled by technology, and be able to support the proper managerial climate for innovative and knowledge-based organizations. By doing so, they would be able to redefine the scope of the HRM function by increasing the time that they engage in strategic HRM activities. Though the research gave evidence for the lowered level of dependency on the HRM department, the rise of the HRM function in terms of strategic relevance within the organization due to the web-based HRM system adoption was beyond the scope of this study.

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Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Proposed Research Model

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and correlations among study variables

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 User satisfaction	3.39	.75	-																				
2 System usage	4.25	.82	.17	-																			
3 Size of the organization [†]	-	-	-.14	-.18	-																		
4 Sector of the organization [†]	-	-	.36**	-.19	.19	-																	
5 Age of the web-based HRM system [†]	-	-	-.36**	-.11	.49*	-.30	-																
6 Product type [†]	-	-	.23	-.31	.26	.16	-.30	-															
7 Level of complexity	3.82	1.07	-.27	-.47*	.24	.30	.17	.21	-														
8 Reduced time spent on manual clerical tasks	4.02	.57	.07	.41**	-.50	-.16	-.55**	-.06	-.74**	-													
9 Ensured timely completion of work	3.83	.93	.33*	.37**	-.09	-.57**	-.05	-.22	-.58**	.66**	-												
10 Decreased the time needed to do work	3.65	1.02	.22	.41*	-.23	.09	-.43*	.02	-.47	.69**	.60**	-											
11 Enabled rapid communications	4.43	.87	.43*	.72**	.14	-.45*	.25	-.18	.057	.08	.64**	.16	-										
12 Ensured cost savings	4.24	.56	.06	.46*	-.31	-.22	-.40**	.15	-.62	.83**	.66**	.79**	.18	-									
13 Faster reactions to problems/ opportunities	3.98	.96	.39**	.27*	.36*	-.12	.65**	-.06	.59**	-.28	.17	-.15	.58**	-.17	-								
14 Increased control over operations	3.88	.85	.04	.40**	.04	-.17	-.40	.16	.05	.272	.61**	.47*	.38	.29	.32*	-							
15 Reduced interruptions	3.68	.77	.24	.04	-.40	-.47*	.06	-.04	-.66**	.54**	.57**	.42	-.18	.57**	-.22	.15	-						
16 Increased amount of available data	4.00	1.03	.40**	.11	-.30*	-.28	.08	-.20	-.89**	.41**	.30*	.46*	.19	.70**	-.19	-.16	.66**	-					
17 Provided better access to needed data	4.33	.96	.27	.42**	-.13	.21	.08	-.59**	-.10	.01	-.01	.09	.35	-.31	-.01	.02	-.06	.60**	-				
18 Improved decision making	3.77	1.23	.13	.33*	-.08	-.01	.10	.56**	.18	.09	.14	.61**	.29	.41	.29	.29	.46*	.57**	.50**	-			
19 Increased speed in document retrieval	3.82	1.00	.21	.32*	-.33*	-.40**	.34	-.02	-.28	.18	.20	.22	.42*	.39	.13	-.19	.57**	.66**	.16	.62**	-		
20 Age [†]	-	-	-.23	-.09	-.34*	-.37**	.28	-.20	-.33	.01	-.12	-.15	-.11	.09	-.29*	-.60**	.34	.31*	-.16	-.17	.43**	-	
21 Gender [†]	-	-	.19	.05	.06	.07	-.41*	.14	-.09	-.04	.06	.43*	-.11	.16	-.21	.42**	.07	-.08	.06	.05	-.28	-.25	-
22 Prior experience with IT-based HRM systems at previous work places [†]	-	-	.20	.11	-.01	-.09	-.01	.49*	-.22	.33*	.48**	.57**	.26	.55**	.18	.30**	.42*	.37**	.07	.61	.39**	-.04	.02

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

[†] Binary-coded variables

Appendix 1:

The measurement of the variables was as follows:

- Web-based HRM modules deployed (availability) - a list of 18 web-based HRM modules was provided. Invited the respondent to indicate the web-based HRM modules that exist in his/her organization by circling a “yes/no” option. The option “other” was also added to the list to state any other web-based HRM modules deployed, which were not offered by the questionnaire.
- The degree of usage of each web-based HRM module- invited the respondent to indicate the degree of usage of each web-based HRM module over a normal period of one month duration using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- Level of complexity of the system- invited the respondent to indicate using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- User satisfaction- invited the respondent to indicate his/her overall satisfaction with the web-based HRM system using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- System usage- invited the respondent to indicate his/her overall usage of the system over a normal period of one month duration using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- Perceived usefulness of the web-based HRM system- for all the perceived usefulness related variables, invited the respondent to indicate using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- The extent to which web-based HRM system led to devolve HRM workload to employees- invited respondents to indicate using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘very low’ to (5) ‘very high’;
- Age- invited the respondent to indicate his/her age;
- Gender- invited the respondent to indicate his/her gender by circling the relevant option;
- Prior experience with IT-based HRM systems at previous work places- invited the respondent to indicate by circling a “yes/no” option;
- Size of the workforce of the organization- invited the respondent to indicate the number of employees in the workforce;
- Sector of organization- invited the respondent to indicate by circling the relevant option;
- Age of the web-based HRM system- invited the respondent to indicate the age of the web-based HRM system;
- Product type- invited the respondent to indicate by circling the relevant option.